

Franchise Entrepreneur: Strengthening a Restricted Identity

Empreendedor Franqueado: Fortalecimento de uma Identidade

Restrita

Empresario Franquiciado: Fortalecimiento de una Identidad

Restringida

Recebido

Received

Recibido

Janeiro, 2025

January, 2025

Enero, 2025

Aceito

Accepted

Aceptado

Março, 2025

March, 2025

Marzo, 2025

Publicado

Published

Publicado

Abril, 2024

April, 2024

Abril, 2024

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e_ISSN

2965-3339

DOI

10.29327/2384439.3.3-3

São Paulo

v. 3 | n. 3

v. 3 | i. 3

e33264

Abril-Junho

April-June

Abril-Junio

2025

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Abstract: The article has a general objective to describe the importance of a specific type of entrepreneur, namely the franchisee entrepreneur. Thus, a research methodology classified as exploratory and qualitative, based on bibliographic analysis, was adopted through an interview with an entrepreneur, using a script composed of open-ended questions, characterizing a case study. Being possible to identify with the help of the general objectives that it is possible to maintain and even strengthen the franchised brand, even if you are a franchisee entrepreneur, by identifying guidelines and restrictions of the brand, evaluation of practices adopted by already established franchisees and in the analysis of communication and the relationship between both parties for strengthening the brand, also considering strategies to maintain and strengthen the brand of a franchise, considering the specific limitations and opportunities. Among the main findings, based on a comprehensive and detailed examination of the dynamics governing franchises in minimarkets, it was found that the importance of franchisor support and the need to adapt to local demands are crucial despite the benefits of a medium-risk and emerging market venture.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship; Franchise; Brand; Strategies.*

Resumo: O artigo tem como objetivo geral descrever a importância de um tipo de empreendedor em específico o empreendedor franqueado. Desse modo, foi adotada uma metodologia de pesquisa classificada como exploratória, de caráter qualitativo, com base em análise bibliográfica, por meio de entrevista presencial com um empreendedor, aplicado um roteiro composto por perguntas abertas, caracterizando um estudo de caso. Sendo possível identificar com a ajuda dos objetivos gerais que é possível manter e até fortalecer a marca franqueada, mesmo sendo um empreendedor franqueado, mediante a identificação de diretrizes e restrições da marca, avaliação de práticas adotadas por franqueados já estabelecidos e na análise da comunicação e o relacionamento entre ambas as partes para o fortalecimento da marca, considerando ainda estratégias para manter e fortalecer a marca de uma franquia, as limitações e oportunidades específicas. Dentre os principais achados, no que tange aos resultados obtidos que com uma visão abrangente e detalhada das dinâmicas que regem as franquias de minimercados, verificou-se a importância do

suporte da franqueadora e a necessidade de adaptação às demandas locais, apesar dos benefícios de um empreendimento de médio risco e emergente no mercado.

Palavras-chave: Empreendedorismo; Franquia; Marca; Estratégias.

Resumen: El artículo tiene como objetivo general describir la importancia de un tipo de emprendedor en particular el emprendedor franquiciado. De esta manera, se adoptó una metodología de investigación clasificada como exploratoria, de carácter cualitativo, basada en análisis bibliográfico, por medio de entrevista presencial con un empresario aplicado un guión compuesto por preguntas abiertas, caracterizando un estudio de caso. Siendo posible identificar con la ayuda de los objetivos generales que es posible mantener e incluso fortalecer la marca franquiciada, aun siendo un emprendedor franquiciado, mediante la identificación de las directrices y restricciones de la marca, evaluación de las prácticas adoptadas por los franquiciados ya establecidos y en el análisis de la comunicación y la relación entre ambas partes para el fortalecimiento de la marca, considerando también estrategias para mantener y fortalecer la marca de una franquicia, considerando las limitaciones y oportunidades específicas. Entre los principales hallazgos, en lo que se refiere a los resultados obtenidos, con una visión amplia y detallada de las dinámicas que rigen las franquicias de pequeños supermercados, se comprobó la importancia del apoyo de la franquiciador y la necesidad de adaptación a las demandas locales, a pesar de los beneficios de un emprendimiento de mediano riesgo y emergente en el mercado.

Palabras clave: *Emprendimiento; Franquicia; Marca; Estrategias.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Globalization and the expansion of franchise networks have transformed the business landscape, offering entrepreneurs the opportunity to partner with established brands. However, this relationship presents significant challenges, particularly in managing the franchised brand.

For the franchisor, brand standardization and consistency are essential to maintaining its reputation and market recognition. On the other hand, the Franchisee, although benefiting from the use of an already established brand, often faces the need to adapt franchise strategies to the particularities of its local market without compromising the brand identity.

This dynamic raises the question about the possibility of maintaining and even strengthening the franchised brand, even as a franchised entrepreneur, which constitutes a relevant issue in the context in which the success of a franchise depends on the capacity of each franchised unit to replicate the business model successfully, despite facing specificities of regional markets.

The Franchisee, as an independent entrepreneur, seeks to maximize his return and ensure the viability of the business but to do so, he needs to balance the mandatory guidelines of the franchisor with the innovation necessary to meet the specific demands met, thus better understanding the dynamics that guarantee shared success between franchisor and Franchisee.

This article aims to explore the various dimensions of the relationship between a franchisee and a franchisor by examining how franchisees can contribute to strengthening the brand, even when operating under restrictions imposed by the franchisor. The role of the Franchisee in this process will be discussed, as well as the best practices and strategies that can be adopted to keep the brand strong and relevant in different markets, based on interviews and bibliographical studies, analyzing strategies to maintain and strengthen the brand of a franchise, considering the specific limitations and opportunities of the franchisee entrepreneur.

Furthermore, the article seeks to identify the guidelines and restrictions imposed by the franchisor that affect the Franchisee's autonomy in managing the brand, making a comparison between the autonomous entrepreneur and the franchised entrepreneur, in addition to evaluating the best practices adopted by franchisees who managed to strengthen the brand, respecting the franchise rules and analyzing how communication and the relationship between franchisor and Franchisee can impact the strengthening of the brand.

The relevance of this study lies in the growing importance of franchises in the global market and the need to understand better the dynamics that guarantee shared success between franchisor and Franchisee, consequently demonstrating that brand growth can be leveraged through different approaches to franchises, but following the same objective and standardized identification, in order to better understand the dynamics that guarantee shared success between franchisor and Franchisee.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

To address the composition proposed in this study, it is necessary to understand the basic historical notions about entrepreneurship, specifically the figures of franchisee entrepreneurs and franchisors. Additionally, it is essential to provide examples of franchising in practice and reference successful franchise models.

2.1 Franchise business

The franchisee entrepreneur is one of many possible profiles in the business world. According to the Brazilian Micro and Small Business Support Service (Sebrae), this type of entrepreneur acquires the right to use an already established brand through a contract with the franchisor, who is the creator and developer of the business. By investing in a franchise, the franchisee entrepreneur acquires the right to use the brand, products, services, and business model of an established company and must adhere to the guidelines and standards established by the franchise.

When joining a franchise, the entrepreneur must adhere to the standards already established by the franchisor. When considering joining a franchise system, the future entrepreneur must keep in mind that he will be joining a type of club where he must follow a set of established rules.

Franchises arise from the difficulty of monitoring the growing number of units owned by franchisees. Due to geographical distance, franchisor owners transfer control from managers to franchisees, believing that the franchisees' efforts will contribute to the business's success as if they were managers (Melo and Andreassi, 2010).

The franchise system is one of several methods for expanding a company's operations and distributing its products in the market. In this business relationship, there are two fundamental roles: the Franchisee and the Franchisor. Both work together to expand and maintain the brand's quality. (Melo and Andreassi, 2010).

The franchise agreement is a contract between two independent companies in which one, the franchisor, transfers to the other, the Franchisee, the right to sell its product and the right to use the brand. In exchange, the Franchisee pays an initial fixed remuneration (franchise fee) and a monthly variable remuneration (royalty fee and marketing fund). This agreement provides for a regional delimitation and a specified period of validity (Melo and Andreassi, 2010).

The relationship between the two is one of partnership, where the success of one is directly linked to the other. The franchisor provides the business model with the necessary support, while the Franchisee applies this model and manages the unit according to the guidelines, serving customers.

This relationship involves the exchange of a series of tangible and intangible resources, with the franchisor as the endpoint. The franchisor is responsible for providing support to establish a new franchise, including training, supplying products, and developing marketing and financial plans. The Franchisee, in turn,

is responsible for marketing the products and services established by the franchisor (Melo and Andreassi, 2010).

This type of entrepreneurship requires some pillars, such as a defined strategy. According to the Michaelis dictionary (2016), strategy is defined as: "The art of using available resources in a planned manner or of exploiting the situation or favorable conditions that one may enjoy advantageously in order to achieve certain objectives." By using appropriate strategies, it is possible to expand, strengthen and manage the business effectively.

In this sense, the franchisor network plays an active role, providing training, support, guidance, and sharing best practices observed. The franchisor network must plan to expand and then structure itself to serve new franchisees.

In this way, there is an improvement in the process of evaluating and selecting franchisees, aiming to increase the chances that the Franchisee will be directly involved in the business, managing the store and its team closely, rather than expecting the franchisor network to assume all responsibility for the work.

Successful franchise strategies combine careful and effective planning, execution, and a continued focus on adaptation and innovation. By implementing the right strategies, a franchise network can grow sustainably while maintaining brand consistency and meeting the needs of both franchisees and customers.

Brand management is also a key aspect of a franchisee entrepreneur's responsibilities. This management involves improving and developing actions to represent the product or service in the market, such as its name, images, and logo, thereby differentiating it from others. It is an ongoing process of applying strategies to consolidate the company in the market, from creating visual identity characteristics to the way of serving and interacting with customers.

Strengthening a brand in the market is crucial to a company's success. This challenge extends beyond creating a visual identity to maintaining that identity in the customer's mind. Companies that are better remembered and better known tend to be more successful. Effective visual communication brings together elements that convey all the qualities of the business, characterizing the brand and solidifying its uniqueness in the market. A project aligned with the brand's positioning, purpose, and values is essential (Sebrae, 2024).

2.2 Franchisee vs Franchisor

The relationship between the Franchisee and franchisor is one of the primary characteristics that distinguishes the franchise model from other business models. This relationship must be built on mutual trust, respect, and transparency, as both parties depend on each other's success to achieve their established goals. The franchisor is responsible for providing the expertise, technical knowledge and brand, while the Franchisee assumes the management of the local operation.

According to Bittencourt (2012, p. 45), The relationship between the Franchisee and the franchisor is a partnership that, to be successful, needs to be supported by a clear

and detailed contract in which the responsibilities and obligations of both parties are established. The franchise contract plays a central role, as it outlines the obligations of each party, the rules of operation, and the use of the brand. Continuous communication between the parties is crucial for aligning expectations and resolving problems as they arise.

Hence, knowledge transfer is a key factor in the success of this relationship. The franchisor must ensure that the Franchisee receives adequate training and ongoing support to maintain the standards of the franchise network. According to Castro (2015), the training provided by the franchisor plays a crucial role in ensuring the uniformity and success of operations across different locations, enabling the Franchisee to address the challenges of the local market effectively.

The strategies adopted by franchise chains are essential for growth and maintaining competitiveness in the market. These strategies involve standardizing products and services offered, as well as defining operational processes that can be replicated efficiently and effectively across different units.

According to Vasconcelos (2016), the primary attraction of the franchise system is its ability to replicate a successful business model across multiple locations while maintaining quality and consistency in the customer experience. This standardization not only strengthens the brand but also enables franchisees to benefit from the expertise developed by the franchisor while maintaining autonomy in managing their units.

Another strategic aspect is the support offered by the franchisor. This support may include selecting a commercial location, developing marketing plans, managing supply logistics, and monitoring results. The ongoing support of the franchisor is one of the reasons that makes the franchise system so attractive to entrepreneurs who want to minimize risks and maximize their chances of success (Souza, 2018).

Furthermore, international expansion strategies are a growing trend among large franchise chains. Franchises that already have a consolidated brand in their country of origin can explore new markets through internationalization, adapting their business model to the cultural and regulatory specificities of other countries. According to Moura (2017, p. 123), the internationalization of franchises is a strategy for diversifying risks and increasing competitiveness, offering new revenue streams and enhancing the brand's visibility.

One of the primary benefits of the franchise system is the strengthening of the brand, which becomes a valuable asset for both the franchisor and the franchisees. The strength of the brand is one of the main attractions for the Franchisee, who enters the business with the advantage of working with a brand that is already established and recognized by the public.

According to Dias and Lima (2014), brand strengthening is the result of a combination of marketing strategies, quality management, and continuous innovation. The franchisor's role is to protect and promote the brand, ensuring that franchisees strictly adhere to the established standards to maintain the brand's integrity in all units. Standardization of products and services is essential for the brand to maintain a consistent identity and be recognized wherever the

franchise is located (Silva, 2019).

Investment in advertising campaigns and *branding actions* by the franchisor contributes to strengthening the brand in the market. This type of investment not only benefits the network but also yields direct benefits for franchisees, who can experience an increase in demand for their products or services.

Although the franchisor plays a leading role in managing the brand and formulating strategies, the success of a franchise also depends heavily on the performance of the franchisees. They are responsible for the day-to-day operation of the unit and for implementing the strategies and guidelines provided by the franchisor.

The Franchisee must, therefore, act as an actual manager of his business, being proactive in seeking improvements and monitoring financial results. The Franchisee must have an entrepreneurial profile and be willing to follow the standards defined by the franchisor while seeking ways to adjust the business to the specific characteristics of his local market (Costa, 2015).

Nevertheless, the Franchisee must maintain a close relationship with the franchisor, communicating regularly to resolve problems and seek guidance whenever necessary. The success of a franchised unit depends on constant communication and cooperation between the parties involved.

It is worth noting that the Franchisee also has the responsibility to safeguard the brand's reputation and maintain the quality of the products or services offered. The Franchisee is responsible for safeguarding the brand in his/her area of operation, and his/her performance directly impacts the way consumers perceive the network as a whole. (Pereira, 2018).

The relationship between a Franchisee and franchisor, when well-managed, can generate mutual benefits and ensure success for both parties. Standardization of processes, ongoing support and brand strengthening are some of the elements that make the franchise system attractive to entrepreneurs. Although the role of the Franchisee is essential for the local operation to be successful, it requires management skills and a commitment to franchise standards.

Strengthening the relationship between the Franchisee and the franchisor is essential for success, as the exchange of ideas promotes a favorable environment for innovation and improvement of the services provided.

According to the magazine example, in a network, the challenges of keeping franchisee employees well-informed become greater. For this reason, Andreassi (2008) points out that the Franchisee must maintain good, open, and constant communication with the franchisor, which includes providing feedback, reporting operational problems, and suggesting improvements.

Relationships between firms are considered relational resources that aggregate the strategic resources and skills developed by franchisors and franchisees through their daily operations (Melo and Andreassi, 2010).

The relationship between the Franchisee and the franchisor is a partnership in which the role of each party must be clear so that they can work together,

respecting agreements and rules to achieve a common goal. It is the franchisor's responsibility to provide training and ongoing support that the Franchisee must follow. The Franchisee is responsible for operating the business by establishing guidelines and regulations, maintaining good communication, and seeking help and guidance whenever needed.

2.3 Franchisee vs Independent Entrepreneur

Below, we highlight some favorable and unfavorable aspects of creating a franchise model. This approach is crucial for achieving the specific objectives of this study, which involves verifying the strengthening of a franchised brand and its limitations, as well as analyzing the advantages and disadvantages of remaining as a franchisee or establishing one's own business independently.

When joining a franchise, one negative aspect is related to subordination, as the Franchisee, in practice, is not their boss. He submits to a hierarchical structure within his company, following the guidelines of the franchisor, under the premise that the latter has greater knowledge about the best ways to manage the franchise.

Among the positive aspects, the presence of a partnership stands out. The Franchisee counts on the franchisor as a partner, sharing both the profits and the risks of the business. On the other hand, the independent entrepreneur assumes full responsibility for their business without the ongoing support that characterizes the relationship between a franchisor and Franchisee.

Another negative point for the Franchisee is related to the lack of autonomy in decision-making. The business depends, to a large extent, on the Franchisee's limited freedom to make their own decisions, such as creating new products, services, or marketing campaigns, which may be dictated by the franchise agreement. Consequently, an initially positive aspect, such as the support of the franchisor, may become unfavorable since the independent entrepreneur would assume all the risks on his own, unlike the Franchisee, who shares these risks with the franchisor (Leite, 1991).

The franchisor already has an established distribution network, with a brand that has been consolidated in the market after several product tests, which guarantees advantages such as special discounts on the purchase of raw materials, products and/or supplies. In contrast, the independent entrepreneur enters the market with a new and unknown brand, running the risk of not being accepted by the public.

Consequently, it is necessary to pay for the use of the brand, which prevents faster product development in line with market demands. On the other hand, this varies depending on the product since the franchisor, in theory, has more resources to carry out this task. Once completed, the result is passed on to the Franchisee, who does not need to worry about creating the product and is solely responsible for verifying consumer acceptance.

Typically, developing new products involves high costs. In this sense, the advantage lies with the independent entrepreneur when it comes to rapid and

low-cost changes. On the other hand, the independent entrepreneur can meet the needs of his consumers more quickly. In contrast, the Franchisee has to wait for the franchisor to develop new products and pass on the innovations or changes to the franchise network.

The choice of location is an advantage for the independent entrepreneur, who has the freedom to decide where to establish their business. In some cases, the Franchisee depends on the approval or selection of the franchisor. Location is essential for a business's success, and the Franchisee should avoid locations with unfavorable characteristics, such as low proximity to customers, a lack of security, or a saturated market (Foster, 1995).

Regarding advertising costs, in the franchise system, these expenses are generally shared by the entire network, which reduces the cost for each unit. The independent entrepreneur, on the other hand, is responsible for paying for advertising campaigns alone, which can result in high costs.

One positive aspect for the independent entrepreneur about the Franchisee is the freedom regarding their inventory, being able to purchase from any supplier and in the quantity they want. On the other hand, the Franchisee faces limitations in their inventory, as most franchise contracts require them to acquire products, materials, equipment, and/or supplies exclusively from the franchisor or suppliers indicated, licensed, or authorized by them. This restriction in purchasing power often prevents the Franchisee from taking advantage of good acquisition opportunities, as they cannot acquire goods or services from third parties at lower prices (Cherto, 1988).

Finally, concluding this comparison between a franchised entrepreneur and an independent entrepreneur, the latter has the freedom to sell the business, as the independent entrepreneur can dispose of their business whenever they wish, unlike the Franchisee, who is bound by the stipulations in the franchise agreement.

2. 4 A franchise in practice

The relationship between the Franchisee and the franchisor is a fundamental partnership in the franchise system, based on trust and cooperation. This relationship is defined by a clear contract established by law, as provided for in Law No. 13,966/2019, which governs the business franchise system (franchising) and specifies the responsibilities and rights of both parties. The success of the partnership between the franchisor and Franchisee depends on effective communication, constant support, and the preservation of the standards defined by the brand, which are fundamental elements for the business's success (Andrade, 2017).

The Franchisee is not just a business manager but rather a strategic partner who, together with the franchisor, collaborates to expand the brand and preserve its competitiveness in the market (Ribeiro, 2019). This collaboration enables the franchisor to maintain control over the brand and its processes. At the same time,

the Franchisee has the freedom to manage local operations, thereby maintaining the integrity of the business.

The strategies employed by franchise networks are crucial to ensuring the efficient replication of the business model. They involve the standardization of products and services, along with rigorous quality control. The primary advantage of franchises lies in their ability to offer a proven and standardized business model, thereby minimizing risks for the Franchisee and increasing the chances of success (Chiavenato, 2014).

Implementing marketing strategies and defining clear operational guidelines enable the brand to be recognized consistently, regardless of the unit's location. The success of franchises is closely tied to effective standardization strategies and continuous innovation, which ensure that the brand remains relevant and appealing to consumers (Meirelles, 2016).

Brand building is one of the main benefits for franchisees. Successful franchises invest in branding and marketing to ensure that their products or services are recognized in the market. The strength of a brand within a franchise system is one of the primary elements of success, as it provides franchisees with the support of an already established brand, thereby strengthening consumer confidence (Greco, 2018).

The franchisor plays a crucial role in protecting and promoting the brand. Maintaining high-quality standards is crucial to ensure the brand remains associated with excellent products or services. Strict quality oversight and consistency in consumer experience are essential to maintaining the brand's value in the marketplace (Nassar, 2015).

The Franchisee plays an active role in managing the local operation and the success of the unit. While following the guidelines set forth by the franchisor, the Franchisee is responsible for the day-to-day running of the business, which includes dealing with customers, managing employees, and maintaining financial control. The Franchisee is responsible for implementing the business plan in their local area, and their ability to manage the operation has a direct impact on the success of the unit (Las Casas, 2015).

Therefore, the Franchisee must be proactive in their communication with the franchisor and in their marketing initiatives. The Franchisee must understand the local market and adjust the franchise strategies to ensure that the brand remains relevant and competitive (Bittencourt, 2014).

The franchise system has become one of the most effective ways to expand a business. The Franchisee plays an essential role in this success, as we have seen in the previous chapters, from the application of brand standards to brand management and the relationship with the franchisor. As mentioned by the franchising expert, a franchisee who maintains open communication with the franchisor can make a positive contribution to the overall development of the business (Oliveira, 2023).

The Franchisee is responsible for the daily management of the Franchisee. According to José Carlos de Almeida (2020), "the Franchisee is the front line of

the business. Their direct performance directly impacts the customer's perception of the brand (our translation)." This means that the dedication and commitment of the Franchisee are essential to guarantee the quality of the service and customer satisfaction. They are also responsible for inventory management, employee management, and process optimization, which can significantly impact the success or failure of the franchise. Franchisees face numerous challenges that require a remarkable ability to reinvent themselves and adapt according to the needs of the franchisee entrepreneur. The ability to reinvent themselves and adapt to new market conditions is what distinguishes the successful Franchisee (Lima, 2020).

Communication between the franchisor and the Franchisee is also essential, as it must always be aligned with the established guidelines and, at the same time, report challenges and feedback that can improve and contribute to the brand's development.

With the increased competitiveness of the market, those who stand out are those who are willing to learn and actively contribute to strengthening the brand. According to Almeida (2020), "The franchisee is not just a manager; he is a brand ambassador (our translation)."

2.5 Examples of successful franchises

Numerous companies follow the franchise model; the Boticário group follows a methodology in this modality that strictly follows the visual identity based on the responsibility of control and orders according to the needs of the points of sale by the franchisee entrepreneur, without any type of link to the entrepreneur's image and following guidelines from the parent company (franchisee brand).

Another great example in the market, which gained visibility due to sales figures made available on easily accessible websites, is the Subway company. This company also follows a methodology for visual identity at locations and procedures, but it is the entrepreneurs' direct responsibility to request replenishment. This has damaged the brand in the eyes of customers due to the limited availability of specific units' ingredients, resulting in a loss of positive visibility among consumers.

The application of this type of entrepreneur can be exemplified by Thiago Pereira, a franchisee entrepreneur of the *Smart Store chain*, which offers exclusive self-service to condominium residents, company employees, or even in small locations where entry is restricted to a select group of people.

With the franchise purchase process, the brand is promoted through its financial link, and its name is publicized, though it lacks a distinct visual identity. The logo is disseminated, providing comfort to users and visibility to the network. *Merchandising* is typically proposed directly by the Franchisee and suppliers, and merchandise replenishment is also carried out by the entrepreneur, allowing for flexibility and influence on net profit.

The inspection of the facilities is conducted with the assistance of the Franchisee and the landlord. With the careful selection of locations, the control of defaults

is minimal. The net return begins approximately one and a half years after the aforementioned Franchisee; nonetheless, as these are activities of a minimum nature, the replacement and handling of stocks, as well as market research, become automatic requirements in daily life.

In general, the entrepreneur states that this type of organization is of medium risk, which is attributed to the feeling of tranquility regarding fiscal responsibility. Therefore, it is a profitable business with a quick return, counting on brand support and flexibility for dissemination and/or marketing of the enterprise according to the location and public established there.

3. METHOD

The franchising model works, and it can be managed effectively based on the existing royalty rates in the market. The application of bibliographic research, complemented by a qualitative analysis of companies, was further enhanced through direct dialogue with an entrepreneur working in the franchise sector.

Initially, the bibliographical survey provided a theoretical foundation, presenting evidence of thoughts from great authors in the niche of entrepreneurship, which encouraged a response to the problem presented. Aiming to highlight franchising concepts, these examples also serve as a support for external consultations in academic articles and virtual content.

Ten recognized writers on entrepreneurship provided the theoretical basis but with an analytical vision that emphasized the application of franchised entrepreneurship within companies active during the research period. This approach also highlighted the possible strengths and weaknesses within a brand or in its purchase, as well as the advantages and disadvantages of being a franchised entrepreneur.

As this is a relatively recent modality, the bibliographies do not specifically address the term "franchisee entrepreneur"; therefore, adjustments were made to the topic in question.

The podcast format allows the interviewee to express their opinions and experiences freely while still addressing specific topics, such as a questioning script that can assist with research. It also enables the interviewee to be relaxed enough to cover related subjects that may not be in the script but are still pertinent to the collection of information.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interview was conducted with entrepreneur Thiago Pereira, 31, a resident of Mogi das Cruzes. He decided to invest in a business as a franchisee after several attempts to establish new brands in the market, which had not been successful due to the period during which he attempted to do so. As a single father with a seven-year-old son, the need for a balance between two sources of income made it impossible to perform both activities.

As a franchisee entrepreneur, he mentioned numerous training courses on how to maintain the brand and preserve the invested working capital. Despite the flexibility regarding purchasing and replenishment, an inventory control technique was developed to organize the routine together with the family. Every day that he replenishes the stock, there is control through a spreadsheet directly related to the sales system. In this way, he replenishes the missing products from the Smart Store network's markets daily, avoiding defaulters and empty shelves.

During the interview, aspects such as the difficulties faced, profitability, the benefits of an active brand in the market, competition and how brand support is assessed were discussed. Accordingly, the feedback obtained indicated that one of the difficulties was establishing a control method to avoid losing the audience and defaults. Despite the medium-term return, the enterprise considers itself profitable, primarily due to the entrepreneur's time management and prioritization, which enable him to address professional issues without compromising his personal life.

An established brand in the market brings with it corporate responsibility and, consequently, greater public adherence to the business. Competition between locations within a given location is not common, so different brands in this segment have differentials that ultimately help each other. Support, in turn, is evaluated as satisfactory since a customer service center is available 24 hours a day to franchisees, with chatbots and attendants during business hours.

On the other hand, according to the interviewee, the positioning presented in consolidating a business in the franchise modality, despite being considered a medium-risk approach, requires full engagement and commitment from the entrepreneur to achieve the profitability generally sought.

5. CONCLUSION

The positive and negative aspects of the franchise system were analyzed, including issues such as difficulties in starting the business, choosing the location, initial support, dependence on the franchisor, advertising and publicity funds, costs involved, acquisition of stock, development of new products/services, supervision of franchises and the quality of assistance provided.

Considering what was observed, and based on the interview with a franchised entrepreneur, it was concluded that, when well managed, the franchise offers greater chances of success compared to an independent business, as it presents a considerable number of advantages and the cost-benefit ratio of the franchise was considered quite favorable by the interviewees.

The study reveals that franchised entrepreneurs have seen an increase in revenue compared to independent businesses, which corroborates the literature that points to franchises as safer models with greater support for entrepreneurs despite having both positive and negative aspects for both types of entrepreneurs. Franchisees also expressed a positive perception regarding the support from the franchisor and the partnership established.

Despite economic challenges, such as the pandemic, most franchisees remained optimistic about the future, reflecting the resilience of entrepreneurs and generally receiving institutional support from the franchise. Nevertheless, the contradiction between the support received and the dissatisfaction with the lack of flexibility in the guidelines suggests that franchisees' expectations of autonomy often do not align with the reality of the rigid business model.

This highlights the need for franchisors to reassess their operational policies, striking a balance between compliance and the individuality of each Franchisee to enhance both performance and satisfaction.

The research highlighted the ease provided by the franchise system's structure, as expressed by the interviewee and bibliographic studies. Strengthening the brand by the Franchisee can be a positive point if there is active communication between the parties and the attribution of personal characteristics to the business is avoided. The expansion of an already-established brand into new segments represents a medium-risk challenge. Nonetheless, it is also an objective that many entrepreneurs seek, incorporating a personal aspect into their professional endeavors.

It is essential to recognize that external factors, including the local economic climate and prior experiences with other business models, can influence franchisee satisfaction. For this reason, it is recommended that future research adopt a longitudinal approach to analyze the evolution of satisfaction and performance over time, addressing legal issues to deepen the understanding of the franchise system, as outlined in Law No. 13,966/94.

This research provides a foundation for future investigations into the relationship between franchisees and franchisors, highlighting the importance of understanding the factors that influence performance and satisfaction in this sector. The success of a franchise system depends on the ability of both parties to adapt to market expectations, promoting a cycle of growth and fulfillment for all.

In short, franchisees play a crucial role in the Brazilian economy, and their experiences are diverse. Support from franchisors, combined with greater flexibility in operations, can benefit both individual success and the strengthening of the franchise system. An ongoing dialogue between the franchisor and Franchisee is essential to create a collaborative environment that fosters growth and innovation.

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